

Table 1.

Population of the United States Virgin Islands: 2010 and 2020

Geographic area	Population		Change (2020 less 2010)	
	2010	2020	Number	Percent
United States Virgin Islands	106,405	87,146	-19,259	-18.1
Island and Subdistrict				
St. Croix Island	50,601	41,004	-9,597	-19.0
Anna's Hope Village subdistrict.....	4,041	3,282	-759	-18.8
Christiansted subdistrict.....	2,626	1,866	-760	-28.9
East End subdistrict.....	2,453	2,336	-117	-4.8
Frederiksted subdistrict.....	3,091	2,303	-788	-25.5
Northcentral subdistrict.....	4,977	4,197	-780	-15.7
Northwest subdistrict.....	4,863	3,431	-1,432	-29.4
Sion Farm subdistrict.....	13,003	10,332	-2,671	-20.5
Southcentral subdistrict.....	8,049	7,415	-634	-7.9
Southwest subdistrict.....	7,498	5,842	-1,656	-22.1
Island subdivision not defined.....	0	0	0	X
St. John Island	4,170	3,881	-289	-6.9
Central subdistrict.....	779	470	-309	-39.7
Coral Bay subdistrict.....	634	724	90	14.2
Cruz Bay subdistrict.....	2,706	2,652	-54	-2.0
East End subdistrict.....	51	35	-16	-31.4
Island subdivision not defined.....	0	0	0	X
St. Thomas Island	51,634	42,261	-9,373	-18.2
Charlotte Amalie subdistrict.....	18,481	14,477	-4,004	-21.7
East End subdistrict.....	8,403	7,502	-901	-10.7
Northside subdistrict.....	10,049	8,889	-1,160	-11.5
Southside subdistrict.....	5,411	4,112	-1,299	-24.0
Tutu subdistrict.....	6,867	5,129	-1,738	-25.3
Water Island subdistrict.....	182	164	-18	-9.9
West End subdistrict.....	2,241	1,988	-253	-11.3
Island subdivision not defined.....	0	0	0	X
Town and Census Designated Place (CDP)				
Charlotte Amalie town.....	10,354	8,194	-2,160	-20.9
Charlotte Amalie East CDP.....	2,491	1,908	-583	-23.4
Charlotte Amalie West CDP.....	5,644	4,404	-1,240	-22.0
Christiansted town.....	2,433	1,770	-663	-27.3
Coral Bay CDP.....	605	615	10	1.7
Cruz Bay CDP.....	2,866	2,772	-94	-3.3
Frederiksted town.....	859	528	-331	-38.5
Frederiksted Southeast CDP.....	2,168	1,746	-422	-19.5
Red Hook CDP.....	350	225	-125	-35.7
Tutu CDP.....	7,356	5,519	-1,837	-25.0

X Not applicable.

Note: The areas named "Island subdivision not defined" consist of offshore water and small uninhabited islands, not assigned to any subdistrict. Populations of the subdistricts are mutually exclusive and sum to the island total. Towns and CDPs may be in more than one subdistrict. Populations of the towns and CDPs do not sum to the U.S. Virgin Islands total.

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, 2010 Census of the U.S. Virgin Islands and 2020 Census of the U.S. Virgin Islands.

DRB Clearance CBDRB-FY22-009